

IBPG - Darwin

The Institute of Biopaleogeography
named under Charles R. Darwin

IBPG 25 (2024) 1-109

E-ISSN 2956-4573

Cultural expedition through Romania

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Publisher's Address:

Scientific Publishing House DARWIN at The Institute
22, Adama Mickiewicza Street, 78-520 Złocieniec,
District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

Cite of this article:

Fabio Rossano Dario, Maria Cristina Veiga De Vincenzo. Cultural expedition through Romania. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin 25 (2024) 1-109*

ABSTRACT

This paper is a photographic summary of a cultural expedition in September 2008 in Romania to learn a little about this incredible country's natural and historical-cultural beauties. The photos show some medieval cities, fortifications, castles, monasteries, museums, and churches with iconographic paintings registered.

Keywords: Romania, tourism, culture, traditional people, iconographic painting

INTRODUCTION

The main objective of this cultural expedition, realized in September 2008 was to know Romania, in a safe and pleasant trip through its rich culture and natural beauty. We know medieval cities, fortifications, castles, monasteries, churches with iconographic paintings, archaeological sites, and many museums (**Figure 1**). We had contact with friendly Romanian people, always willing to provide information and with delicious Romanian food. Fabio Rossano Dario and Cristina De Vincenzo took the photos presented in this report using a cell phone and digital photo camera.

Our arrival in Romania was via Constanța airport. Constanța is a beautiful and historic city, bathed by the Black Sea. It is Romania's oldest continuously inhabited and the country's largest seaport. Its history is more than 2,500 years. Originally called Tomis, founded by Greek colonists from Miletos in the 6th century BC, it was conquered by the Romans in 71 BC, and renamed Constantiana by Roman Emperor Constantine the Great, in honor of his sister. The Roman poet Ovid (43 BC - 18 AD), in the year 8 AD, was banished from Rome by Emperor Augustus, living the last years of his life in Constanța. Constanța flourished during the 13th century but began to decline two centuries later when it fell under Turkish rule. During the Ottoman era, its name was shortened to Constanța. In 1878, after the Romanian War of Independence, Constanța, and the rest of Northern Dobruđa were ceded by the Ottoman Empire to Romania [1-6].

The Constanța History and Archaeology Museum, in Piața Ovidiu (Ovid Square), is a central square of the old quarter with a statue of the exiled Roman poet Ovid. The architecture is beautiful, in Romanian Revival style. The archaeological collections at this museum are invaluable (**Photo 1**). In Piața Ovidiu we can also see the Grand Mosque of Constanța. The mosque is referred to by Constanța's Islamic community as the King's Mosque. The mosque was built at the beginning of the 20th century, in Neo-Egyptian and Neo-Byzantine styles with elements of Neo-Romanesque architecture. The minaret, built in Neo-Moorish style, has a height of 47 meters, from where you have a beautiful view of the Black Sea (**Photo 2**).

The Constanța Casino, built in 1880, is located on the seafront along the Black Sea. It is a symbol of the city of Constanța, in Art Nouveau style. During the communist period, the casino was transformed into a House of Culture, and in 1956, the building was declared part of the national patrimony. Unfortunately, the building has remained closed since 1990 (**Photo 3**). Constanța's beaches, located on the Black Sea, are popular with the local population and tourists and are recognized for their clean sand and pleasant water conditions (**Photo 4**).

Figure 1. Romania Map (Google).

Charming Bucharest (București), the capital of Romania, is one of the most beautiful cities in Europe. Walking around the city, what impresses us most is the large number of public gardens and the architecture, made up of beautiful French neoclassical buildings and elegant Haussmannian buildings, surrounded by Bauhaus style buildings [7], built in the communist period, in the reconstruction of the city, as Bucharest suffered significant damage from bombing, during Second World War.

With around two million inhabitants, București is full of museums, that match the cultural richness of the Romanian people. The National Geological Museum (Muzeul Geologic Național) hosts a collection of 80,000 samples of rocks, fossils, and minerals from Romania. The building (**Photo 5**), built in 1907 for the Geological Institute of Romania is an attraction, in the Romanian Revival style [8], that appeared in the late 19th century in Romanian Art Nouveau.

Another museum we visited in București was the National Art Museum of Romania, located in the Royal Palace (**Photo 6**). This museum has collections of medieval and modern Romanian art, as well as a rich international collection assembled by the Romanian royal family. In the museum garden, it is possible to admire sculptures by Ștefan Ionescu-Valbudea (1856-1918) (**Photo 7**). The modern Romanian collection features sculptures by Constantin Brâncuși (1876-1957) and Dimitrie Paciurea (1873-1932). Brâncuși is considered one of the most important sculptors of the 20th century, pioneering the technique of direct sculpture, instead of working with intermediaries such as plaster or clay models.

Museum rooms were filled with paintings by Theodor Aman (1831-1891), Nicolae Grigorescu (1838-1907), Theodor Pallady (1871-1956), Gheorghe Petrașcu (1872-1949), and Gheorghe Tattarescu (1818-1894) (**Photo 8**). Romanian painters are very talented, and we fell in love with Nicolae Grigorescu: his portraits of peasant women and rural landscapes are

stunning (**Photo 9**). The international collection includes works by El Greco, Tintoretto, Vasari, Bronzino, Jan van Eyck, Jan Brueghel the Elder, Pieter Brueghel the Younger (**Photo 10**), Peter Paul Rubens, Rembrandt, Claude Monet, Sisley, Renoir, and Pissarro.

The Romanian Athenaeum (Ateneul Român) is a concert hall in the center of Bucharest. It is considered one of the most beautiful theaters in the world, inscribed on the List of Historical Monuments, as an architectural monument of first importance, of national and universal value. British and American air raids in 1944 damaged the building, which was later restored. The circular building is the home of the George Enescu Philharmonic Orchestra (**Photo 11**). In the historic center of Dâmbovița, it is possible to admire squares, unique buildings, historical monuments, the Dâmbovița River Linear Park, and walking along the Union Boulevard (Bulevardul Unirii), the former Boulevard of the Victory of Socialism arrive at Palace of Parliament (Palatul Parlamentului), the largest building in the world, commissioned in the late 1970s by the then President of the Socialist Republic of Romania Nicolae Ceaușescu to be the seat of all political and administrative power in Romania. The chief architect was Anca Petreșcu (1949-2013), and the work was carried out during the 1980s (**Photos 12-16**).

Bucharest is a city very well served by subway. Arriving at the Aviatorilor station, we visited the Village Museum (Muzeul Național al Satului Dimitrie Gusti), which is in Parcul Herăstrău (Herăstrău Park). The museum is a huge open-air ecomuseum, where we were able to see beautiful constructions of Romanian rural houses. Opened in 1936, the museum shows aspects of rural life between the 17th and 20th centuries and the traditions of Romanian peasants. There are 123 complexes of traditional architecture, with 363 buildings, including houses, wooden churches, and industrial facilities, which include workshops, windmills, and some hydraulic installations. The houses are all furnished, with household items, furniture, and decorations. The museum's collection also includes more than 50,000 traditional objects. The Village Museum is a result of theoretical and field research work over more than a decade by sociologist Dimitrie Gusti (1880-1955) (**Photos 17-22**).

We visited the National Museum of the Romanian Peasant (Muzeul Național al Țăranului Român), recommended by our dear friend Claudia Mureșan, an admirer of culture and popular art (**Photos 23, 24**). This museum, considered the main museum of popular arts and traditions in Europe, shows a little of Romanian history, through a collection of textiles, icons, handmade tiles ceramic pieces, and other artifacts from Romanian peasant life. Its collection includes over 100,000 objects. In a classroom decorated with botany and morphology boards, we learned that "porumb" is corn, "orez" is rice, "grâu" is wheat, and "ovăz" is oats. We also discovered that in Romania there was an agrarian reform, through land nationalization that transformed large agricultural properties into state or collective farms, significantly increasing agricultural productivity and the quality of life of peasants. During this same period, there were several benefits from the State for the population, such as extra remuneration for peasants who produced more than the minimum expected.

Cișmigiu Park (Grădina Cișmigiu) is an excellent option to spend a whole day, walking in the shadows of linden trees (*Tilia chordata*), frasines (*Fraxinus excelsior*), oaks (*Quercus robur*), chestnut trees (*Sphaerotherium hippocastaneum*), beeches (*Fagus sylvatica*) and firs (*Abies spp*). It is one of the large parks in the city of Bucharest and is in the center. In 1779, the site was an abandoned forest surrounding a lake. This beautiful park was designed in 1845 by the Austrian landscape architect Carl Meyer (1817-1852), who brought 30,000 trees and plants from the Romanian mountains and Vienna's botanical gardens. The name "Cismigiu", comes from the Turkish "çeşme" that means "public fountain". It is a large garden with fountains,

monuments, and a large lake, where you can rent rowing boats in the summer (**Photos 25, 26**) or skate on the ice rink that it transforms into in the winter. In the center of the park, architect Ion Mincu (1852-1912) built the Monte Carlo restaurant. This restaurant was rebuilt after its destruction during a US bombing raid on Bucharest in Second World War, but you can still find details of the "neo-Romanian" style that is so particular to Mincu.

Heading north, towards the Carpathians, we pass through the city of Sinaia, where we visit Mănăstirea Sinaia (**Photos 27, 28**), an Orthodox monastery built in 1695, which is included in the List of Historical Monuments of Romania. Sinaia Monastery is not only home to three hundred years of history, but also a true museum of Romanian art and spirituality.

Braşov, located 170 km from Bucharest, is a beautiful city in the Transylvania region, surrounded by the Carpathians. It is known for its medieval Saxon walls and bastions, and the huge Black Church (Biserica Neagră). Council Square (Piaţa Sfatului) is surrounded by colorful baroque buildings and is home to the Sfatului House, which was the seat of the municipal administration for more than 500 years and is currently home to the Braşov District Museum of History (Muzeul Judeţean from Istorie din Braşov). It is a building with Gothic, Renaissance, and Transylvanian Baroque characteristics, revealing the successive changes it has undergone over the centuries. The Black Church (Biserica Neagră), a Lutheran cathedral, is an incredible Gothic monument. Its construction began in 1477, and its name comes from the fact that it was blackened by the smoke of the great fire of 1689, which destroyed most of the city. We visited the first Romanian school (Prima şcoală românească), located next to the Church of Saint Nicholas. The foundation is probably 1395. We visited the first classroom in Romania: Anton Pann classroom (1790-1854, was a great Romanian poet, folklorist, lexicographer, and textbook author). The school operated until 1941, and in 1964 it was converted into a museum, which in addition to school objects and book collection, has the first Bible written in Romanian and the oldest mobile printing press in Romania, used by Diaconul Coresi (?-1583), who translated and printed the first books from Cyrillic into Romanian (**Photos 29-38, 49**).

Near Braşov, we visited three very peculiar places, in the company of the beloved couple Marius and Beatrice: Râşnov, Bran, and Peleş. In Râşnov there is a stone fortress built in the 13th century by Teutonic knights on a 150-meter-high cliff, formerly called Cetatea Țărănească or Peasant Fortress (**Photos 39-40**). In this citadel, there is a museum of feudal art, where aspects of local history, customs, and crafts of the region, objects, and weapons are presented. The Teutonic Order was a crusading military order linked to the Catholic Church, to assist Germans injured in the Crusades. In 1211, at the invitation of King Andrew II of Hungary (András II Árpád Hiérosolymitai), part of the Order established itself in Transylvania to protect the country's borders, and during their presence in the region, they built fortresses and founded the city of Braşov [9, 10].

Bran Castle is a national monument in Romania, located on the border between Transylvania and Wallachia. Known as "Dracula's Castle", it is promoted as the residence of the character that gives the title to Bram Stoker's novel, who appropriated the fact that this castle was the residence of Prince Vlad Țepeş, governor of Wallachia. The first document that mentions Bran Castle (Castelul Bran) is an act issued by Louis I of Hungary, dated November 19, 1377. From 1920, the castle became a royal residence of the Kingdom of Romania. It was the main residence of Queen Maria of Romania. In 1948, the castle was nationalized by the communist regime and transformed into a museum and heritage of the Romanian people. In 2005, about to join the European Union, the Romanian government passed a special law that allowed the return of assets nationalized by the communist government in 1948 to their

"legitimate owners", in the case of Bran Castle, an architect from New York. Attached to the castle is an open-air museum park (Muzeul Satului Brănean), where traditional Romanian peasant structures are displayed, such as huts and barns, representing the entire country (**Photos 41-46**).

Prince Vlad III of Wallachia became synonymous with vampires in Western literature and cinema, without even having links with the creatures of the night. For most Romanians, leader Vlad was a great defender of the country, freeing Christian Romania from Turkish swords, and stopping the advance of the Ottoman Empire in the 15th century [11].

Peleş Castle (Castelul Peleş), 19th century, considered one of the most luxurious palaces in Europe, is situated in the Carpathian Mountains. Its architectural style is a mix of romantic neo-Renaissance and neo-Gothic inspiration. The interior decoration features mainly Baroque influences. The castle has a rich collection of art from eastern and central Europe, which includes statues, two thousand paintings, including Canaletto, Tintoretto, Velasquez, and Rubens, furniture, stained glass, weapons and armor, gold and silver pieces, Sèvres and Meissen porcelain, tapestries and carpets. The collection of weapons and armor, with more than 4,000 pieces, is very well preserved, with war artifacts from more than four centuries of history. All rooms are furnished with extreme luxury and decorated down to the smallest details. Oriental carpets have several origins, namely Bukhara, Mosul, Saruch, Isparta, and Smyrna (**Photos 47-48**).

Before continuing our journey, we ate the delicious kürtőš, a sweet of Hungarian origin, which is roasted over coals around a wooden cone. We watched the entire kürtőš production process: the dough is rolled into a thin strip around a cone and while it is being baked, it receives successive caramel toppings. When the kürtőš is ready and still hot and caramelized, it receives a topping of nuts, coconut, or sesame, depending on the customer's wishes. This delicious sweet is eaten in strips that emerge in a spiral. We also tried the delicious "gogosi cu smântână și dulceață" (gogosi with cream and jam). Gogosi is what they call "papanashi" in the Braşov region. Papanashi is a traditional Romanian fried or boiled dough. Papanashi dough can be fried, as a "doughnut", or boiled, as a dumpling, like large gnocchi.

Ascending towards Bucovina, we pass through pine forests and agricultural fields, which were formerly cultivated in cooperative associations. However, with the end of the communist period, taking advantage of the economic fragility that Romania was going through, foreign entrepreneurs bought a large part of the lands of Romanian peasants at low cost, which generated an exodus of these families, from the countryside to cities and also outside the country. What we see today along the roads are remaining peasant houses, where agricultural products grown by families, such as onions, potatoes, and pumpkins, are sold at their doors, amidst the extensive plantations of transgenic corn owned by multinationals. The fight is unequal and merciless, because, unlike multinationals, the Romanian peasant, orphaned by State support, survives today with his few resources, using animal traction in agricultural activities and transporting products (**Photos 50-64**).

We arrived in Bucovina, almost on the border with Ukraine, to see the main monasteries painted inside and out, by hand, with scenes from the Old and New Testaments. True works of art in the open air and declared a World Heritage Site by UNESCO [12]. We start at the Voroneţ Monastery (Mănăstirea Voroneţ), built in 1488 and known as the "East Sistine Chapel", all frescoed inside and out, with beautiful icons where the intense blue predominates over the other colors (albastru Voroneţ), which together Veronese's green and Tiziano's red, appears in all international art catalogs. Almost an entire external wall was frescoed with the genealogy of

Jesus Christ. Another facade dramatically depicted the scenes of the Last Judgment, all incredibly well preserved throughout these five centuries of history. The names of the saints are all written in Cyrillic. The shade of blue remains a mystery to everyone, no one has managed to reproduce, it until today, the blue of Voroneț (**Photos 65-80**).

In the Humor Monastery (Mănăstirea Humor), the color red (roșul) prevails on the icons. Built-in 1530, this monastery has modest dimensions with a dome that gives the impression of floating. His paintings refer to a poem dedicated to the Virgin Mary for "saving" the citadel from the Persian attack in the year 626. We climbed a tower using a very narrow staircase, from where we had a beautiful view of the surrounding pine forests (**Photos 81-89**). The small Arbore Monastery (Mănăstirea Arbore) was undergoing meticulous restoration, as a large part of the iconographic paintings were partially destroyed. The predominant color of the paintings in this monastery, built in 1502, is green (Verde) (**Photos 90-98**). The Putna Monastery (Mănăstirea Putna) is not frescoed on the outside, is very large, and was built between 1466 and 1469. It was designed to serve as a royal necropolis for Stephen the Great (Ștefan cel Mare) and his family. Stephen the Great is famous for building and influencing the construction of dozens of churches and monasteries throughout Moldova. The entire surrounding area is made up of rose gardens, in a very peaceful environment (**Photos 99-106**).

In the Sucevița Monastery (Mănăstirea Sucevița) the iconographic paintings highlight the colors red and green (roșu și verde). This beautiful monastery is the largest of all the monasteries in Bucovina and has the largest collection of iconographic paintings. The monastery resembles a medieval fortress, built between 1582 and 1584, in the style of Moldavian architecture, during the reign of Stephen the Great. The church is surrounded by a wall, with four towers in the middle of a beautiful forest landscape. On the south wall is painted the "Tree of Jeseu", a symbol of the continuity between the Old and New Testaments, and on the north wall the "Ladder to Paradise" (scara virtuților), where red-winged angels accompany a line of people trying to climb to the top. sky. A virtue is written on each step and sinners who fall down the stairs are taken by demons (**Photos 107-124**).

In the Moldovița Monastery (Mănăstirea Moldovița) yellow (galben) is the predominant color in the beautiful iconographic paintings. Built in 1532, this monastery has walls completely covered in frescoes, from the marquees to the foundations, where scenes from the Last Judgment can be seen. The facade is dominated by the Hymn to the Virgin and the Tree of Jeseu, painted on a light blue background. Inside, furniture from the 15th century is preserved. There are also paintings about the Siege of Constantinople, in the year 626. The frescoes were inspired by a poem dedicated to the Virgin Mary for having protected Constantinople from the attack of the Persians. Among the paintings, some graffiti can be seen, with people's names, dating from the 19th century, vandalism of a work of art, scraping the wall creating a low relief (**Photos 125-136**).

After this magnificent itinerary through the most beautiful monasteries in Bucovina, we leave this region and continue through the Carpathian Mountains (Munții Carpați) to Transylvania. We passed through dense forests and climbed a Carpathian Mountain. We passed through the Borgo Pass, a place that inspired the Irish writer Bram Stoker to write the story of Dracula [13], the diabolical vampire count of the Székés Transylvanians, an ethnic group that was in Transylvania, "the land located beyond the dense Romanian forests", the starting from the 7th century. We pass through cultivated fields, beautiful rural landscapes, and beautiful cities such as Bistrița and Reghin until we arrive in Târgu Mureș, a beautiful and large city. In

the city center, a beautiful equestrian statue of Avram Iancu (1824-1872), the liberator of Transylvania (**Photos 137-146**).

Arriving in Sighișoara with a full moon is stunning. Sighișoara is an incredible city, full of history, in the heart of Transylvania [14]. A UNESCO World Heritage Site, it has been a Roman, Hungarian, and German city, and is considered the most beautiful, well-preserved, and inhabited citadel in Europe, with authentic medieval architecture. In Eastern Europe, Sighisoara is one of the few, and in Romania the only fortified city that is inhabited. A place where time seems to have passed and you can go back to the medieval era. Inside medieval fortress (Cetatea Medievală) everything is reminiscent of times gone by, the narrow stone streets, the ancient monuments with immense history. We entered via Stradela Turnului, passing under the Turnul cu Ceas, an immense clock tower, 64 m high and built in 1556 and which was formerly the main entrance to the Citadel. The clock dates from 1648 and is made up of 80 cm figures carved in wood that represent characters from the Saxon pantheon. Above are seven figures, each representing a day of the week. We passed by the house where Count Dracula (Vlad Țepeș, the Impaler) was born in 1431. Then we climbed the Scara Acoperită, a staircase with 172 steps covered by a wooden roof, built in 1642, which led us to a beautiful view of the region and to a garden where you can find the Gothic Biserică din Deal (Church on the Hill), built in 1345, where there is an attached school. In front of the main door of this church is the German Cemetery, which conveys calm and peace in the middle of a forest. We visited the Muzeul de Arme Medievale, the Camera de Tortură, and climbed the clock tower (Turnul cu ceas), from where we had a wonderful view of the medieval city. There are several towers scattered along the wall, each representing a guild that played an important role for the city in the Middle Ages: guilds for tanners (tăbăcarii), tinsmiths (cositorarii), goldsmiths (aurarii), ropemakers (frânghierii), butchers (măcelarii), furriers (cojocarii), weavers (țesătorii), tailors (croitorii), shoemakers (cizmarii), locksmiths (lăcătușii), farriers (dogarii), barbers (bărbierii), blacksmiths (fierarii), and the Clock Tower (și Turnul cu ceas). The city's architecture is a mix of Gothic, Renaissance, and Baroque elements, all in perfect balance (**Photos 147-152**).

The region between Sighișoara and Făgăraș is stunning, with dozens of borgos and fortifications that depict the history of Transylvania. We pass through old abandoned borgos of Saxon origin, with fortified churches (cetatea săsească cu biserică fortificată). Apold (**Photos 153, 154**) is an abandoned borgo, built by German immigrants in the 13th century. The view from the top of the tower is of incredible scenic beauty and from there we were able to see the groupings of Saxon and gypsy (Rom) houses. In groups of Saxon origin, the houses are arranged in a line (**Photo 155**), and in gypsy groups, the houses are arranged in a circle (**Photo 155, 156**). Then we passed by the biserică fortificată of Netus (**Photo 157**), also of Saxon origin and abandoned, and Brădeni (**Photo 158, 159**), where we saw the cetatea săsească cu biserică fortificată. It lies in the middle of the Transylvanian Plateau, on the banks of the river Hârtibaciu.

We know two other fortified Saxon fortress with church (cetatea săsească cu biserică fortificată) near Făgăraș: Cincu and Cincșor (**Photos 160-162**). Cincu was first mentioned in a document of 1329 as Schenck, a word connected to Schenke, meaning "tavern" in German. The village was founded in the mid-12th century by some 30 families of German settlers from the Rhineland area in present-day Germany. Historically, the local economy was dominated by agriculture and by craft production organized into guilds for joiners, furriers, harness makers, locksmiths, carpenters, tailors, blacksmiths, cobblers, coopers, wheelwrights, and bricklayers. Located between Sibiu and Brașov, Făgăraș Fortress, built in the 14th century, played an

important role in the history of Transylvania. It is an incredible fortified borgo (cetatea fortificată) (**Photo 163**) surrounded by a huge moat with water and very well preserved [15].

We ended our trip through Romania by visiting Sibiu, a beautiful city, the European capital of culture in 2007, one of the most important cultural and university centers in Romania, with fantastic architecture, mixing Baroque, Gothic, and Renaissance styles. Sibiu was founded in 1190 by German colonists and was one of the main cities of the Transylvanian Saxons. As a result, the local architecture is typically Germanic. The monuments, the wealth of museums, and the natural beauty of the surrounding region contribute to Sibiu being one of the most popular tourist destinations in Romania. We walked through the historic center (Cetatea Medievală), Piața Mare, Piața Mică, Catedrala Evanghelică (in Gothic style, built between 1370-1520), the beautiful and central Palatul Brukenthal, Biserică Romano-Catolică (in Baroque style, built between 1726-1733), Pasajul Aurarilor (a nice passage connecting Piața Mică and Piața Aurarilor), Turnul Sfatului (a 14th-century tower), Strada Nicolae Bălcescu, Generalilor House, the 15th century Gothic Haller House, Turnul Scărilor (13th-century tower), Pasajul Scărilor (built in the 13th century, with a beautiful arch) and the House Artelor, a building from 1370, where there is the Folk Art Galleries (Galeriile de Artă Populară) and the sale of handicrafts, such as the black ceramics of Marginea (**Photos 164-177**).

We visited the "Astra" Museum of the Traditional Folk Civilization (Muzeul Civilizației Populare Tradiționale "Astra"), the "mill museum", which our friend Claudia had recommended. Simply wonderful, an immense park, built starting in 1963, as part of the program to enhance Romanian culture, with immense oaks, forests of linden, fir, pine, and chestnut trees, an immense lake, wooden buildings from almost all regions of Romania, and many mills, of all types and sizes. This open-air museum is in the Dumbrava Forest, 3 km south of Sibiu. It was opened to the public in 1967. Beginning in 1971, it started to orient itself towards folk civilization by also including elements of folk life such as houses and community buildings. Occupying an area of 0.96 square kilometers, it is the largest open-air museum in Romania and one of the largest in Europe. It contains houses and workshops of the traditional Romanian folk culture from the pre-industrial era. Over 300 houses and other buildings are situated in the forest around two artificial lakes with over 10 km of walkways between them. Some of the most spectacular buildings are a group of windmills from the Dobruja area, a few watermills, houses of shepherds, pottery workshops, iron workshops, and others (**Photos 178-194**). On our return to Bucharest, we passed through the Olt valley, between the Southern Carpathians (Carpații Meridionali) mountains, bordering the Olt River, with beautiful landscapes (**Photos 195, 196**).

CONCLUSIONS

Romania is one of the most beautiful countries we have ever visited, and we recommend it to everyone who wants to have a safe and pleasant trip, rich in culture and natural beauty. The country is discreetly crossed by the romantic Danube River, which meets the Black Sea after a long journey. More than half of the Carpathians are in Romania. These mountains hold incredible ancient stories, the testimony of which are medieval cities, fortifications, castles, monasteries, churches with iconographic paintings, archaeological sites, and a large number of museums, where clothing, dwellings, and a wide variety of instruments used by different

peoples that have formed the rich Romanian culture over centuries of history. The Romanian people are very friendly, and the cuisine is extraordinarily tasty.

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Photo 1. Constanța History and Archaeology Museum (Muzeul de Istorie Națională și Arheologie), Constanța, Romania.

Photo 2. The Grand Mosque of Constanța (Marea Moschee din Constanța), Romania. Observe the statue of the poet Ovid in the lower left corner.

Photo 3. The Constanța Casino (Cazinoul din Constanța), transformed into a House of Culture by communists, has remained closed since 1990.

Photo 4. Constanța's beaches, located on the Black Sea (Marea Neagră), are popular with the local population and tourists and are recognized for their clean sand and pleasant water conditions.

Photo 5. The National Geological Museum (Muzeul Geologic Național), București, Romania.

Photo 6. The National Art Museum of Romania (Muzeul Național de Artă al României), București, Romania.

Photo 7. Sculpture by Ștefan Ionescu-Valbudea in the National Art Museum of Romania garden, București, Romania.

Photo 8. National Art Museum of Romania (Muzeul Național de Artă al României), București, Romania.

Photo 9. Painting by Nicolae Grigorescu: Garden Fence. Muzeul Național de Artă al României, București, Romania.

Photo 10. Painting by Pieter Bruegel the Younger: The Four Seasons: Autumn. Muzeul Național de Artă al României, București, Romania.

Photo 11. The Romanian Athenaeum (Ateneul Român) is a concert hall, the home of the George Enescu Philharmonic Orchestra, București, Romania.

Photo 12. The historic center of Dâmbovița, București, Romania.

Photo 13. The historic center of Dâmbovița, București, Romania.

Photo 14. The historic center of Dâmbovița, București, Romania.

Photo 15. Union Square (Piața Unirii) is crossed by Union Boulevard (Bulevardul Unirii), the former Boulevard of the Victory of Socialism. Observe the Palace of Parliament (Palatul Parlamentului) in the background, București, Romania.

Photo 16. Palace of Parliament (Palatul Parlamentului), the largest building in the world, București, Romania.

Photo 17. National Village Museum (Muzeul Național al Satului Dimitrie Gusti), București, Romania.

Photo 18. National Village Museum (Muzeul Național al Satului Dimitrie Gusti), București, Romania.

Photo 19. National Village Museum (Muzeul Național al Satului Dimitrie Gusti), București, Romania.

Photo 20. National Village Museum (Muzeul Național al Satului Dimitrie Gusti), București, Romania.

Photo 21. National Village Museum (Muzeul Național al Satului Dimitrie Gusti), București, Romania.

Photo 22. National Village Museum (Muzeul Național al Satului Dimitrie Gusti), București, Romania.

Photo 23. National Museum of the Romanian Peasant (Muzeul Național al Țăranului Român), București, Romania.

Photo 24. National Museum of the Romanian Peasant (Muzeul Național al Țăranului Român), București, Romania.

Photo 25. Cișmigiu Park (Grădina Cișmigiu), București, Romania.

Photo 26. Cișmigiu Park (Grădina Cișmigiu), București, Romania.

Photo 27. Sinaia Monastery (Mănăstirea Sinaia), Romania.

Photo 28. Sinaia Monastery (Mănăstirea Sinaia), Romania.

Photo 29. Braşov District Museum of History (Muzeul Judeţean from *Istorie din Braşov*) in Council Square (Piaţa Sfatului), Romania.

Photo 30. Orthodox cathedral (*Catedrala Ortodoxă din Braşov*) in Council Square (Piaţa Sfatului), Romania.

Photo 31. Braşov, Transilvania, Romania.

Photo 32. Bibliotheca Johannes Honterus din Braşov, 16th century. Honterus (1498-1549) is known mainly for his activities in geographical and cartographic activities, as well as for his implementation of the Lutheran reform in Transylvania.

Photo 33. The Black Church (Biserica Neagră), 15th century, Braşov, Romania

Photo 34. Braşov, Transilvania, Romania.

Photo 35. Church of Saint Nicholas (Biserică sf. Nicolae) and the first Romanian school (Prima școală românească), 15th century.

Photo 36. Strada Republicii with baroque-style statues, Brașov, Romania.

Photo 37. Braşov, Transilvania, Romania.

Photo 38. Braşov, Transilvania, Romania.

Photo 39. Peasants' Fortress (Cetatea Țărănească), 13th century, Rașnov, Romania.

Photo 40. Peasants' Fortress (Cetatea Țărănească), 13th century, Rașnov, Romania.

Photo 41. Bran Village Museum (Muzeul Satului Brănean), Bran, Romania.

Photo 42. Bran Village Museum (Muzeul Satului Brănean), Bran, Romania: aspects of the peasant family (aspecte gospodării țărănești).

Photo 43. Bran Village Museum (Muzeul Satului Brănean), Bran, Romania.

Photo 44. Bran Village Museum (Muzeul Satului Brănean), Bran, Romania.

Photo 45. Bran Castle (Castelul Bran), Romania.

Photo 46. Bran Castle (Castelul Bran), Romania.

Photo 47. Forest surrounding the Peleş Castle (Castelul Peleş), Romania.

Photo 48. Peleş Castle (Castelul Peleş), Romania.

Photo 49. Detail of a nice Trabant: a symbolic car from the communist era made in East Germany, registered in Braşov, Romania.

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Photo 51. Orthodox Church (biserică ortodoxă) in Băile Tușnad, Romania.

Photo 52. Honey sales point on the road between Șoseaua Gheorgheni and Piatra Neamț, Romania.

Photo 53. Cheile Bicazului Hășmaș National Park, between Șoseaua Gheorgheni and Piatra Neamț in Romania, is of great scientific interest in geology, geomorphology, paleontology, landscape, and biology.

Photo 54. Country view between Șoseaua Rășinari and Păltinis, Romania.

Photo 55. Country view between Șoseaua Rășinari and Păltinisi, Romania.

Photo 56. Edelweiß (*Leontopodium alpinum*) is, plant species from the Asteraceae family that grows in the mountains.

Photo 57. Corn planting between Șoseaua Târgu Neamț and Fălticeni, Romania.

Photo 58. Rural landscape between Șoseaua Târgu Neamț and Fălticeni, Romania.

Photo 59. Rural residence between Șoseaua Fălticeni and Gura Humorului, Romania.

Photo 60. Șoseaua Rural residence between Șoseaua Fălticeni and Gura Humorului, Romania.

Photo 61. Rural residence between Șoseaua Fălticeni and Gura Humorului, Romania.

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Photo 63. Rural residence between Șoseaua Fălticeni and Gura Humorului, Romania.

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Photo 66. Monastery of Voroneț (Mănăstirea Voroneț), 15th century, Bucovina, Romania, and its walls have been colored blue for 500 years, the composition of which is a mystery.

Photo 67. A side of the Monastery of Voroneț (Mănăstirea Voroneț) and its mysterious blue.

Photo 68. Monastery of Voroneț (Mănăstirea Voroneț), 15th century, Bucovina, Romania.

Photo 69. Monastery of Voroneț (Mănăstirea Voroneț), 15th century, Bucovina, Romania.

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Photo 73. Monastery of Voroneț (Mănăstirea Voroneț): Final Judgment (Judecata de Apoi).

Photo 74. Monastery of Voroneț (Mănăstirea Voroneț): Final Judgment (Judecata de Apoi).

Photo 75. Monastery of Voroneț (Mănăstirea Voroneț): Final Judgment (Judecata de Apoi).

Photo 76. Monastery of Voroneț (Mănăstirea Voroneț), Bucovina, Romania.

Photo 77. Monastery of Voroneț (Mănăstirea Voroneț), Bucovina, Romania. Observe the intense blue, characteristic of the paintings in this monastery.

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Photo 83. Monastery of Humor (Mănăstirea Humor), where the color red prevails.

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Photo 85. Monastery of Humor (Mănăstirea Humor): Final Judgment (Judecata de Apoi).

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Photo 87. Monastery of Humor (Mănăstirea Humor), Bucovina, Romania.

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Photo 100. Bukovina, on the border with Ukraine.

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Photo 102. Putna Monastery (Mănăstirea Putna), Bucovina, Romania, built between 1466-1469.

Photo 103. Putna Monastery (Mănăstirea Putna), Bucovina, Romania.

Photo 104. Putna Monastery (Mănăstirea Putna), Bucovina, Romania.

Photo 105. Putna Monastery (Mănăstirea Putna), Bucovina, Romania.

Photo 106. Putna Monastery (Mănăstirea Putna), Bucovina, Romania.

Photo 107. Welcome.

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Photo 109. Sucevița Monastery (Mănăstirea Sucevița), Bucovina, Romania

Photo 110. Sucevița Monastery (Mănăstirea Sucevița), Bucovina, Romania. The iconographic paintings highlight the colors red and green (roșu și verde).

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Photo 122. Sucevița Monastery (Mănăstirea Sucevița), Bucovina, Romania: exterior wall paintings fresco (frescă exterioară).

Photo 123. Sucevița Monastery (Mănăstirea Sucevița), Bucovina, Romania: exterior wall paintings fresco.

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Photo 127. Moldovița Monastery (Mănăstirea Moldovița), Bucovina, Romania: exterior wall paintings fresco.

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Photo 129. Moldovița Monastery (Mănăstirea Moldovița), Bucovina, Romania: detail of Siege of Constantinople.

Photo 130. Moldovița Monastery (Mănăstirea Moldovița), Bucovina, Romania: detail of Siege of Constantinople.

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Photo 132. Moldovița Monastery (Mănăstirea Moldovița), Bucovina, Romania.

Photo 133. Moldovița Monastery (Mănăstirea Moldovița), Bucovina, Romania: detail of graffiti with people's names, dating from the 19th century.

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Photo 135. Moldovița Monastery (Mănăstirea Moldovița), Bucovina, Romania.

Photo 136. Moldovița Monastery (Mănăstirea Moldovița), Bucovina, Romania.

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Photo 142. Pumpkins (dovleac) are being sold in rural areas, between Șoseaua Reghin and Târgu Mureș. Transilvania, Romania.

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Photo 150. Sighișoara, Transilvania, Romania: medieval fortress (Cetatea Medievală).

Photo 151. Sighișoara, Transilvania: Tinsmiths' Tower (Turnul Cositorarilor): observe the bullet holes in the tower wall.

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Photo 154. Apold, Transilvania: the fortified Saxon fortress with church (cetatea săsească cu biserică fortificată), 13th century.

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Photo 159. Brădeni, Transilvania: Saxon fortress with fortified church (Cetatea săsească cu biserică fortificată).

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Photo 195. Landscape between Șoseaua Sibiu and Râmnicu Vâlcea (Carpații Meridionali): Olt valley.

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